

BOBURNOMA - A RARE SOURCE

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“According to Babur’s philosophy, he is worth loving more than Caesar.”

Eduard Holden.

Annotation: Every country, every nation has its own history, its own statehood, its own beliefs, its own literature, its own legends. El-ulus has been living and developing with these values for centuries. He tries not to forget them out of respect, but to add new ones.

There will be times in the history of the people when there is a growing need to collect and organize the rich heritage of our ancestors, which has been growing from the depths of the distant past, and to educate our contemporaries and future generations on the basis of these spiritual values.

The work “Boburnoma” by the thinker Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483-1530), who became a king and poet of his time, was born in response to such demands and proposals of his time.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (the word “Zahiriddin” means “sergul tree”, “Babur” in Arabic means “lion”) was born on February 14, 1483 in Andijan. His father Umarshaikh Mirzo (1455-1494) was the 5th generation of Amir Temur. Umarshaikh Mirza died on June 9, 1494 in Akhsi fortress with a pigeonhole. His mother, Kutlug Nigorkhanim’s father, Yunus Khan, the governor of Tashkent, was of Uzbekized Mongol descent and was related to Genghis Khan for 12 generations. Babur told his mother, “Genghis Khan’s second son is a descendant of Chigtaykhan”. The support of three women was invaluable in making Bobur a great statesman. Babur Mirzo’s grandmother Eson Davlatbegim, mother Kutlugnigorkhanim and sister Khonzodabegim.¹

¹ Harold Lamb. Bobur - Tiger. - T.: Uzbekiston, 2018. - P. 52.

After the death of his father, Babur ascended the throne of Andijan. The 12-year-old Bobur runs the government with the help of beys such as Sheikh Mazidbek, Boboqli Boboalibek, Qasim Qavchin.²

Babur Mirza fought tirelessly for the throne, capturing Samarkand in 1497, 1500, 1501, Osh and its environs in 1502-1503, and was defeated by Ahmad Tanbal. In 1503, Babur captured Kabul and Ghazni without a fight. In 1506, Babur's mother Kutlug Nigorkhanim died. While in Samarkand, Bobur received a letter from Alisher Navoi, but did not meet.

As a result of Shaybanikhan's pressure, Babur retreated to India and marched on India five times since 1507. On April 12, 1526, at the Battle of Panipat, he defeated the Indian sultan Ibrahim Lodi's 100,000-strong army with an army of 12,000, thus establishing a new dynasty in northern India. Babur Mirza died on December 26, 1530 in Agra. He was buried in the center of Nurafshan Park on the left bank of the Jamna River. In 1533, the khaki, a hypocrite of his will, moved to Kabul ("Babur's Garden").

Babur's place in history, not only did he establish a new dynasty in India as a great commander, but his great service left the Boburnoma to generations. In the play, Babur recounts the events he saw and knew year after year. The work was originally called The Story. Later it was published in such letters as "Vaqoe Boburiy", "Tuzuki Boburiy", "Boburnoma".³

The play depicts the events of 1494-1529 in Movorunnahr, Khorasan, Afghanistan and India. As a result of the Timurids' inability to unite and their ignorance, Movoraunnahr and Khorasan fell into the hands of the Shaybanids and the great Timurid dynasty disintegrated and Babur failed to unite the Timurids. describes what he has suffered. The work mentions not only historical events but also toponymic place names. This adds to the value of the work, so I decided to focus on the names of historical places in the work.

² Sariyev S. Literature. T.: East, 2016. - P. 211.

³ Sariyev S. Literature. - T.: East, 2016. - P. 211.

In the play, Babur describes Fergana, where he was born and raised, and his capital, Andijan, as follows: “Fergana region is in the fifth climate. Kashgar in the east, Samarkand in the west, the border mountains of Badakhshan in the south, although there are cities in the north, such as Almalyk, Olmotu and Yangi Kim, Tarozkent ends in the books, there is no administrator left. It is a short province, rich in grain and fruit. To the west, there are no mountains, except for Samarkand and Khojand. There is no winter in the south except this one. The Sayhun River is famous for its Khojand water, which flows from the east and north, and flows through the region to the west. There are seven bribery towns: five on the south side of the Sayhun River and two on the northwest. One of the southern towns, Andijan, is a mediocre place.” From this it is clear that the borders and provinces of the Fergana Valley were composed of which territories in the 15th century, and that the cities in the north of the valley were divided and destroyed by the Mongols and Uzbeks. He also wrote about Andijan region: “I am from Andijan, the capital of Fergana region. It is not uncommon to sell melons at the beginning of the melon season. There is no better nashpot than Andijan. There is no greater fortress in Movoraunnahr than Samarkand and Kesh. It has three gates. It happened on the south side of the arch. Nine streams of water come in, and it's amazing that it doesn't come out of nowhere. Eli is Turkish. There is no one in the city and market who does not know Turkish. Eli's words are true... There is a huns imagination among Eli. Yusuf Khojakim is famous in music, he is from Andijan. There is a stench of air. There will be a lot of hand malaria in the fall”.⁴

One of the highlights of Boburnoma is that it covers geographical areas in full. From Central Asia to India, it is a historical source that has contributed greatly to the development of the 15th and 16th centuries. He describes the capital of Movoraunnahr as follows: “Samarkand is of the fifth climate. The city is Samarkand, the province is called Movoraunnahr. It is said that a bald man is safe because he

⁴ Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. Boburnoma. - T.: Asterisk, 1989. - Б. 5-6.

does not achieve this with any anger or victory. Samarkand was built by Alexander. The Mongols and Turks call Semizkand a Sunni and pure sect, a mutasharri (meaning Sharia-compliant). It is bounded on the east by Fergana and Kashgar, on the west by Bukhara and Khorezm, on the north by Tashkent and Shohruhiyakim, on the north by Shosh and Banokat, on the south by Balkh and Termez, and on the north by the Kohak River (Zarafshan). The city of Samarkand is a wonderful city, which has one feature that is rare in any other city. Every craftsman has a different market, which is not mixed with each other. There are good breads and cooks. The best paper in the world comes out of this city. Vale is famous for two fruits Samarkanddin: sebi Samarkand (apple type) and owner Samarkand (grape type). He has built two gardens in Samarkand (Amir Temur). There is also a big pavilion in Dilkusho, which depicts Temurbek's war in India".⁵

The borders of Samarkand are also fully covered in the play.

The Boburnoma mentions the importance of other cities in Movoraunnahr, including Kesh and Bukhara, at that time. In particular, the city of Bukhara said that Samarkand is 25 kilometers away, has a lot of good fruits, especially melons, and there is no better wine than wheat. Kesh province is located in the south of Samarkand, nine blocks away, there is a mountain between the cities, it is called Itmak davoni and all the stones are brought from this mountain, Amir Temur built many buildings and structures because he was born in Kesh. The mausoleums of Jahongir Mirzo and Temur's descendants were built in this city.

Babur Mirza not only traveled to the cities and countries of the country to form a state, but also spoke in detail about the nature and form of these lands. In particular, the Boburnoma writes about Kabul and India: "Kabul is the fourth climate. It's in the middle of nowhere. East Lamganat and Pushavor (Peshawar) and Hashangar are some Indian provinces. I am from the western mountains, Karnud and Gur are from there. In this history, the mountains are the abode and abode of the

⁵ Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. Boburnoma. - T.: Asterisk, 1989. - B. 44.

Hazara and Nakdari people. It is northwest of Kunduz and Andarab provinces. Mount Hindu Kush is a tool. South is Farmul and Nagar, Bannu and Afghanistan. It is a short province. It is surrounded by mountains. The castle is connected to the mountain. To the southwest of the fort is a smaller mountain. It is called the King of Kabul because it was built on the top of the mountain. The foothills of this mountain are completely deserted. In the time of my uncle Ulugbek, the father of Weiss dug a ditch at the foot of this mountain. The garden in Doman is full of canals. Poyoni ob Gulkina is a equestrian neighborhood, it is a desert. The victory was won by the Lavenders. To the south of the fort is a large lake to the east of King Kabul. India is one of the two ports on the land route between Khorasan. One is Kabul and the other is Kandahar. The caravan from Kashgar and Fergana, Turkestan, Samarkand, Bukhara, Balkh, Gissar and Badakhshan will arrive in Kabul. It is a province of India and Khorasan. Seven to eight thousand horses come to Kabul every year. Fifteen to twenty thousand caravans from Lower India will arrive in Kabul”.⁶

From the above, we can see that Kabul is an important player in international trade. In Boburnona, Babur also describes India as a country with a completely different climate. The weather is hot, the fruits are plentiful, and the crop can be harvested several times a year, he said. The east and south, but also the west, will be exposed to the ocean. It is a mountain in the north, connected with the Hindu Kush and Kafiristan, and the mountains of Kashmir. Northwest Kabul and Ghazni, Kandahar. Delhi, the capital of the Indian state, is melting. After Sultan Shihabiddin Ghuridin, until the end of Sultan Firuz Shakh’s reign, most of India was on the throne of the Delhi salad.

In this history, I have conquered India, five Muslim kings and two infidels ruled in India. India has a second and third climate. It's happening in a strange country. Our region is a different world. Mountains and rivers, forests, deserts, meadows, animals, plants, people, language, rain, wind are all special events. Sindh

⁶ Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. Boburnoma. - T.: Asterisk, 1989. - P. 116.

water, then land, water, wood, stone, hand, nation, rog, painting is the end of India's development. Most of India's provinces are salt flats. There are several ways to do this: a buckwheat, a crop and a garden do not need water at all, and the person in charge of it knows the rain of Easter. It's weird that the rabbi's crop can be harvested even if it doesn't rain. The saplings are watered for a year or two by a wheel or a drum, and then there is no need to water them. Some vegetables are watered. Lohur, Dibolpur and Sixrind nabohi give water with a wheel. My animal is an Indian elephant. The Indian "hoti" is on the border of Kolpi province. And the higher the east, the more desert elephants there will be".⁷

The "Boburnoma" is divided into three parts according to the course of events described in it: the first - Babur's visit to Movaunnahr in 1494-1504, the second - to Kabul and Kandahar (Afghanistan) in 1504-1524, the third - to India in 1524. The experiences of many people in different situations in 1529 leave information about the many mountains, rivers, forests and deserts, climate, population, social, political, economic situation of Asia. Also, the value of the work is enhanced by the fact that almost 50 years of Babur Mirza's life from Central Asia to India are accurately described

⁷Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur. Boburnoma. - T.: Asterisk, 1989. - P. 250-251